

An Evaluation of Parallel Knapsack Algorithms on Multicore Architectures

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Abstract—*Emergence of chip multiprocessor systems has dramatically increased the performance potential of computer systems. Since the amount of exploited parallelism is directly influenced by the selection of the algorithm, algorithmic choice also plays a critical role in achieving high performance on modern architectures. Hence, in the era of multicore computing, it is important to re-evaluate algorithms efficiency for key problem domains. This paper investigates the impact of algorithmic choice on the performance of parallel implementations of the integral knapsack problem on multicore architectures. The study considers two algorithms and their parallel implementations, and examines several aspects of performance including speedup and scalability.*

Keywords: multicore, algorithms, optimization, parallelism

1. Introduction

It is widely agreed, that the trend of packing more and more cores on a single chip, brought on by the advent of multicore technology, is likely to continue for the next years - perhaps decades. This fundamental shift in processor design technology implies that software plays a key role in harnessing the true potential of any computer system. In particular, compilers need to uncover parallelism at different levels and transform code for parallel execution. Also, run-time systems need to schedule concurrent threads for efficient utilization of underlying architectural resources. For many problem domains, however, advances in performance optimizing software will not be sufficient. To a great extent, the parallelism that can be extracted by the compiler is determined by the initial choice of the algorithm. For example, in the combinatorial optimization field dynamic programming and branch-and-bound algorithms are used to solve optimization problems but these algorithms have different degrees of parallelism and therefore, lead to widely varying performance. Thus, it is important to consider *algorithmic choice* when implementing parallel solutions on current chip multiprocessor (CMP) architectures.

Finding the most suitable algorithm that will deliver high-performance across different architectures and problem sizes has always been a significant challenge, researched over years. In particular, approaches based on automatic tuning have been quite successful for automating the selection of the optimal (or near optimal) algorithmic variant for specific domains [1], [2], [3]. However, the emergence of CMP systems adds a new level of complexity. CMP architectures

contain one or more levels of cache shared among multiple processing cores. A shared-cache (or memory, in general) poses an inherent trade-off between data locality and parallelism [4]. On one hand, any parallel decomposition will inevitably influence the data access patterns from concurrent threads and consequently affect locality. On the other hand, any transformation for improving locality will impose constraints on parallelism that will affect performance. Thus, when parallelizing an application for CMP architectures, it is imperative to find the right balance between data locality and parallelism. Since algorithmic choice dictates the amount of exploited parallelism and data locality, it plays a key role in obtaining high-performance on CMP systems.

This paper studies the impact of algorithmic choice on the performance of parallel algorithms for solving the integral knapsack problem (IKP) under a dynamic programming (DP) approach. Two different DP algorithms are studied. IKP is very relevant in combinatorial optimization because it directly models practical situations such as capital budgeting [5], cutting stock [6], [7] cargo loading problems [8], [9] and scheduling of batch processors [10]. Furthermore, IKP's appear as sub-problems in set-partitioning formulations for multi-dimensional cutting stock [11], crew scheduling and generalized assignment problems [12]. IKP's have also contributed to the generation of minimal cover induced constraints and in the development of coefficient reduction procedures for strengthening bounds for general integer programming (IP) problems [13]. This relationship between IKP's and other IP's has motivated great interest for developing efficient IKP algorithms.

Several factors make IKP a suitable target for evaluating the impact of algorithm choice. IKP algorithms under a DP approach are amenable to different types of parallelism. For example, some IKP algorithms can be parallelized in a pipelined fashion [14] and in other algorithms the central loop lends itself to a data parallel decomposition. Also most implementations of IKP exhibit data locality that can be exploited through compiler transformations.

The primary goal of this study is to understand the performance trade-offs from choosing a particular type of DP algorithm for solving an IKP instance. Specifically this paper makes the following contributions:

- a quantitative analysis of performance for two DP algorithms is presented. To the best of our knowledge, no previous work has looked at performance issues for IKP algorithms on multicore architectures.

- a key *tunable* parameter is identified which can be used to significantly enhance performance of both parallel algorithms

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides background on the IKP; Section 3 describes our experimental methodology; Section 4 presents experimental results and analysis; Section 5 discusses related work on parallelization of IKP; and finally, Section 6 provides conclusions.

2. The Integral Knapsack Problem

2.1 Problem description

IKP can be formulated as follows: Given a knapsack of capacity C and a set of n different objects (items) each one of them with profit p_j and weight w_j , find non-negative integers x_1, \dots, x_n , where x_j represents the number of j th type objects, such that the total weight of the objects does not exceed the knapsack capacity and the total profit is maximized. In the IKP, w_j, p_j, n , and C are all positive integers. If $x_i \in 0, 1$ the problem reduces to the 0/1 knapsack problem.

Some authors refer to the IKP as *unbounded knapsack problem (UKP)* [13]. The UKP assumes that an infinite number of objects of each kind are available while the *bounded knapsack problem (BKP)* assumes that there is up to b_j objects of each type available, that is, $x_j = 1, \dots, b_j$. Following is the IP formulation for the UKP:

Maximize

$$\sum_{j=1}^n p_j x_j \quad (\text{UKP})$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^n w_j x_j &\leq C & j = 1, \dots, n \\ x_j &\geq 0 \text{ and integer, } & j = 1, \dots, n \end{aligned}$$

Even if knapsack problems (KP's) look as the simplest IP's, they are NP-hard [15]. Thus, KP's cannot be solved in a time bounded by a polynomial in n [13]. However, they can be solved with *pseudo-polynomial* algorithms since $\log_2(C)$ bits are required to encode the input C .

2.2 Solution approaches

The classic approaches for solving exactly KP's are branch and bound (B&B) [13] and dynamic programming (DP) [16], [17], [14]. Here the discussion focuses on DP. Hybrid approaches combining DP and IP are also mentioned briefly.

2.2.1 DP forward recursion 1

Works in [6] and [13] presented a DP forward recursion (see Eq. 1) to compute $f_m(\hat{c})$, the total profit (i.e. total value) from loading the most valuable combination if considering m items and a knapsack capacity \hat{c} . In this recursion, l represents a possible number of items to load.

$$f_m(\hat{c}) = \max\{f_{m-1}(\hat{c} - lw_m) + lp_m\} \\ l \text{ integer, } 0 \leq l \leq \lfloor \hat{c}/w_m \rfloor \quad (1)$$

where $m = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $\hat{c} = 0, \dots, C$. After the forward recursion step, the optimal value for the profit function is given by $f_n(C)$. A backtracking step permits to determine the optimal solution $(l_m^*, m = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ associated to $f_n(C)$.

For each m , $O(C \lfloor \hat{c}/w_m \rfloor)$ operations are required to find $f_m(\hat{c})$ and then the overall time complexity is $O(C \sum_{m=1}^n \lfloor \hat{c}/w_m \rfloor)$ or $O(nC^2)$ in the worst case. The space complexity is $O(nC)$, since for each item, the vector $f_m(\hat{c})$ must be stored.

2.2.2 DP forward recursion 2

The work in [18] presented a recursion to the 0/1 knapsack problem which was extended to the integral case by [11] and parallelized by [19]. Authors in [11] mention that this recursion (see Eq. 2) is more efficient than the one in Eq. 1. The recursion is given by:

$$f_m(\hat{c}) = \max\{p_m + f_m(\hat{c} - w_m), f_{m-1}(\hat{c})\} \quad (2)$$

$m = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $\hat{c} = 0, \dots, C$. Equation 2 selects between loading or not a unit of product m . This recursion involves less operations than the one in equation 1 by a factor of $1/n \sum_{m=1}^n \lfloor \hat{c}/w_m \rfloor$ and the resulting time and space complexity are $O(nC)$. Details about the procedures to find the optimal solution $(l_m^*, m = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ associated to $f_n(C)$ are in [11] and [20].

For large IKP's the B&B approach seems more efficient than DP [14]. The instances that B&B can solve are usually larger than the ones DP can solve. However, in contrast to B&B algorithms, DP recursions (equations 1 and 2) are insensitive to the parameters $p_i, w_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and therefore they can be good for non well-behaved problems (i.e. problems with correlated p_i and w_i values) but not so good for well-behaved problems (i.e. uncorrelated problems). DP also exhibits two additional advantages: knowledge of the solution for any capacity lower than the given maximal capacity and ability to reuse the known solutions for solving larger capacity problems [17].

2.2.3 Hybrid approaches

The work in [21] is the first hybrid approach for solving IKP's. The algorithm significantly outperforms all existing algorithms for solving the problem. The algorithm success comes from embedding B&B into a DP framework, applying

multiple bounds including a new stronger one, and exploiting many IKP properties such as dominance relations and periodicity.

2.3 Description of Implemented Algorithms

This paper implements the DP forward recursions 1 [6] and 2 [11] provided in Section 2.2. In the rest of the paper, these two algorithms are referred as `classic` and `morales`. Both algorithms use a two dimensional matrix M of n rows that represent the items and C columns that represent the knapsack capacities. Without loss of generality, the knapsack capacity is in terms of weight but it could be any other dimension to use efficiently such as volume, length, etc. The ordered pair (m, \hat{c}) represents any entry(row, column) in M . From applying any algorithm, entry (m, \hat{c}) stores the maximum attainable value from using integer quantities of items 1, 2, ..., m and a knapsack with capacity \hat{c} . For example, for a knapsack problem with 5 items ($i = 1, \dots, 5$), maximum capacity $C = 8$ kg, and profit and weight vectors, p_i and w_i , respectively, entries at the 1st row of M contain the maximum attainable values if loading only item 1 for different knapsack capacities \hat{c} , the ones in the second row contain the maximum attainable values after loading items 1 and 2, and so on.

Following are particular descriptions for the algorithms studied.

`classic` [6] (Eq. 1 in Section 2.2.1): The algorithm goes through M row by row. For every item m , the maximum number of items of type m that can be loaded given a knapsack with capacity \hat{c} is computed as $\lfloor \hat{c}/w_m \rfloor$. A choice for the number of units of product m to load in the knapsack is notated as l . Given a choice of l units for product m , a possible value for entry (m, \hat{c}) is calculated adding the previous maximum attainable value in row $m-1$ and column $\hat{c} - (w_m * l)$ to the value from loading l units of product m , that is, $l * p_m$. After repeating this computation for all possible values of l , ($l = 0, 1, \dots, \lfloor \hat{c}/w_m \rfloor$), the maximum of these values denoted as $f_m(\hat{c})$ is stored in entry (m, \hat{c}) .

Diagram 1 illustrates the dependence between entries of M for the computation of $f_m(\hat{c})$ if using `classic`.

Fig. 1: Dependence between entries for `classic`

`morales` [11] (Eq. 2 in Section 2.2.2): The algorithm also goes through M row by row. To compute a maximum attainable value for entry (m, \hat{c}) , it compares the value of not using the item m at all, that is the value stored in row $m-1$ at column \hat{c} and the value from using one more unit of current product m which is the sum of the maximum attainable result at entry $(m, \hat{c} - w_m)$ and the value of a single unit of item m , p_m . The maximum of these two quantities is recorded at entry (m, \hat{c}) .

The following diagram illustrates the dependence between entries of M for computing $f_m(\hat{c})$ if using `morales`.

Fig. 2: Dependence between entries for `morales`

3. Parallelization Strategies

3.1 Parallelizing `classic` for CMP

A fairly straight-forward data parallel decomposition is applied for parallelizing `classic`. In `classic`, there is only a single data dependence that goes from the previous row to the current row of matrix (grid) M . Therefore, computation of each element for a given row can be performed in parallel. Each row is divided among the number of threads to obtain different sections. At a time each thread is working on it's own row section and storing the computed values. When all threads have completed their sections then work on the next row begins. The process is repeated until the values in M has been computed completely. Synchronization occurs at the end of each row computation. Blocking was applied to improve data locality within each thread. In this context, the number of blocks results from dividing the total capacity C by block size.

3.2 Parallelizing `morales` for CMP

The parallel implementation of `morales` is based on the simple pipeline algorithm (SPA) presented in [19]. The SPA algorithm targets a distributed system. This paper modifies the algorithm to work on a shared memory architecture. The parallel algorithm is outlined in Fig. 3. Similar to `classic`, `morales`, uses the M grid in which rows represent items and columns represent capacities. There are

```

// n = total number of items
// C = total capacity
// m = item (item/row index in 2D grid M)
//  $\hat{c}$  = capacity (capacity/col index in 2D grid M)
//  $f.aux[\hat{c}] \approx f[m][\hat{c} - weight[m]] + profit[m]$ 

for stage = 1 to (n/NUM_THREADS) do
  m = (stage-1) * NUM_THREADS + threadID
  if (weight[m] ≤ C) then
    f.aux[weight[m]] := profit[m]
  end if
  for  $\hat{c}$  = 1 to C do do
    // getting input? f[m-1][ $\hat{c}$ ]
    lock(cdlock[threadID])
    if (consume[threadID][ $\hat{c}$ ] != true) then
      wait(consume[threadID], cdlock[threadID])
    end if
    consume[threadID][ $\hat{c}$ ]=false
    unlock(cdlock[threadID])
    if ( $\hat{c} \geq weight[m]$ ) then
      f[m][ $\hat{c}$ ] = MAX(f[m-1][ $\hat{c}$ ], f.aux[ $\hat{c}$ ])
    else
      f[m][ $\hat{c}$ ] = f[m-1][ $\hat{c}$ ]
    end if
    if (m + weight[m] ≤ C) then
      f.aux[ $\hat{c}$  + weight[m]] := f[m][ $\hat{c}$ ] + profit[m]
    end if
    // sending output? f[m][ $\hat{c}$ ]
    int nextthread=0
    if (threadID == (NUM_THREADS-1)) then
      nextthread=0
    else
      nextthread=threadID+1
    end if
    lock(cdlock[nextthread])
    consume[nextthread][ $\hat{c}$ ]=true
    signal(consumec[nextthread])
    unlock(cdlock[nextthread])
  end for
end for

```

Fig. 3: Parallel implementation of *morales*

two data dependencies that need to be preserved when parallelizing *morales*. Computation of any value on the grid is dependent on a value from the previous row *and* a value from the same row in a previous column. Because of this dual dependence, neither the rows nor the columns can be run in parallel by themselves. Therefore, this research adopts the pipelined parallelization strategy in *morales*. The entire computation is broken up in stages, and each thread works as both a producer and consumer - consuming values from a previous stage and producing values for the next stage. Threads communicate with each other about the status of the computation of the values in M by setting a two dimensional boolean array. A naive scheme of locking both the producer and consumer at every stage would result in too many synchronizations among the threads. For this reason, thread communication is optimized by simulating a non-blocking sender and a receiver that blocks. At any time,

two adjacent threads work on one row each and the consume array is reused and reset by the threads. The order of setting the *consume* array from true to false with respect to capacity is important. Moreover, the array has to be locked whenever changes to it are made.

The threads in the algorithm in Fig. 3 are communicating and synchronizing one element at a time. However, the amount of computation done by each thread for one element is very little. This results in a large communication overhead, causing

tt morales parallel algorithm to run slower than the sequential counterpart. This research handled this problem by blocking on the capacities, in such a way that communication occurs only after each thread computes a block of columns in M before communicating to the next thread. The total capacity is divided by the block size to determine the number of blocks. As Section 4 shows, block size has a significant impact on the performance of *morales*.

4. Performance Characterization

4.1 Experimental Framework

Each parallel variant is evaluated on two platforms: a 2.33 GHz Intel Core 2 Duo (*Core2*) and 2.40 GHz Intel Core 2 Quad (*Quad*) system. *Core2* contains a 2 MB L2 cache, shared by two cores, whereas *Quad* has two 4 MB L2 caches shared between two cores in each socket. For our scalability study, we also run experiments on an 8-core and 16-core system, with each core running at 2.50 GHz and 1.66 GHz respectively. *classic* is implemented using OpenMP, while *morales* is implemented with pthreads. Both variants are compiled with GCC version 3.4, with the default (-O2) optimization settings. To avoid system jitter, each experimental run is replicated five times and only the consistent lowest values are considered. In some cases, we exclude outlier values, when it is obvious that the extra long running time is due to operating system interference. Wall clock time is measured by embedding calls to openmp timer routines within the source code. When reporting execution times we only report running time for the key loop nest in the application, and thus exclude any overhead associated with calls to timer routines and file I/O operations. For each implementation we limited the number of concurrent threads to the number of available cores on the target machine. Each parallel variant is run with a data set consisting of 10,000 *items* \times 10,000 maximum knapsack capacity, generated using the procedure described in [22].

4.2 Speedup and Scalability

Fig. 4 shows speedup obtained over the sequential version, for both *classic* and *morales* for 2, 4, 8 and 16 cores. This chart reveals that both parallel variants obtain significant speedup over their sequential counterparts. However, *classic* yields higher speedup than *morales* when

Fig. 4: Performance improvement with increasing number of cores

Fig. 6: Impact of block size on performance of parallel morales on *Core2*

Fig. 5: Impact of block size on performance of parallel classic on *Core2*

Fig. 7: Impact of block size on performance of parallel classic on *Quad*

the number of cores is less than or equal 8. When the number of cores is increased to 16, we see that neither algorithm delivers the expected performance. For *morales*, the performance plateaus at 16, whereas for *classic* there is a slight degradation. One possible explanation for this anomaly might be that when the number of threads increases to 16, the synchronization delays from the increased number of threads offsets the performance gains from parallelism. Another explanation might be that the slower processors speed on this platform is having an impact on the relative speedup as well.

4.3 Impact of Blocking Factor and Granularity

As mentioned earlier, the blocking factor controls both the granularity of parallelism and the data locality among concurrent threads. A series of experiments is conducted to evaluate the performance impact of blocking factors for both parallel variants. The results of these experiments are summarized in Figs. 5-8. Figs. 5 and 6 show performance of *classic* and *morales* on *Core2*, as we vary the block sizes. We observe a clear performance trend for both *classic* and *morales*. The performance drops significantly for smaller block sizes, picks up as we increase the block size and then drops again when we increase the block size beyond $5K$. We speculate that the poor performance for smaller block sizes is a result of poor granularity. When block sizes are ≤ 48 , concurrent threads are not assigned enough computation to offset the overhead of thread creation

and synchronization. On the other hand, when we increase the block size to be $\geq 5K$, the working sets become too large to fit into the cache, resulting in poor data locality.

Figs. 7 and 8 present performance results for varying block sizes on *Quad*. An identical performance pattern is observed on this platform. Any block size smaller than 48 or larger than $5K$ turns out to be a poor choice. It should be noted, that although total cache capacity on *Quad* is larger than *Core2*, the available cache per socket is still the same, and thus, the range of good tile sizes appears to be the same for both platforms. The range of good tile sizes are likely to be different for architectures that have cache configurations that are significantly different from *Core2* or *Quad*.

5. Related Work

There is fewer literature on parallelizing the IKP than on parallelizing the 0/1 KP. The related work closest to the one in this paper is in [19]. These authors present multiple strategies for parallelizing the DP recursion 2 proposed by [11] for the IKP. The results are tested in a distributed framework for transputer and LAN networks using occam and PVM, respectively. The first algorithm is a simple pipeline algorithm (SPA) that performs a parallelization on the objects. The implementation is on a one-way ring topology with a root processor to facilitate synchronization and administration of the queue of messages (computed f values).

Authors in [19] do not consider blocking as an alternative

Fig. 8: Impact of block size on performance of parallel morales on *Quad*

to improve the performance of SPA but they implemented SPA with single dominance [7] to reduce the high communication cost between processors. The new algorithm is named pipelined algorithm with dominance (PAD). Only non dominated solutions from a previous row are sent to the next processor to compute 2. A future study may consider to combine dominance and the blocking concept proposed in this research to improve performance for morales algorithm.

Paper in [19] also implemented a pipelined algorithm with parallelization on the capacities (PAPC). For a particular knapsack item, each processor computes the f values for a range of capacities of fixed length r . Dependency may occur among non-adjacent processors and therefore a particular processor may wait for values sent by a processor different to its predecessor. The knapsack items are associated with the iterations or steps of the algorithm. Only after a row of the matrix M is completely computed, the algorithm proceeds with the computations for the next item (row).

Authors in [14] present a parallel pipelined algorithm for the IKP with time complexity equal to the one in [19], that is, $O(nC/q + n)$ where q is the number of processors. The algorithm was implemented on a ring topology and the speedup resulted asymptotically linear on q . Authors also present a new procedure for the backtracking phase with a time complexity $O(n)$, an improvement to $O(mc)$, the time complexity of usual strategies.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This paper explored the issue of algorithmic choice in the context of the IKP by comparing the performance of two parallel variants on multicore platforms. The results reveal that although a row-by-row problem decomposition does not fare well when run sequentially, it exhibits good scalability when run in parallel. Another key finding of this study is that blocking factors have significant impact on performance of each parallel variant. Therefore, to achieve improved performance, it is necessary to select blocking factors through careful analysis. Future research will explore effects on performance of the parallel variants to changes in

data set sizes. The data locality aspects of performance will also be examined in more depth.

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